

Graph Neural Networks for Predicting Solvability of Finite Groups

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Abstract

We present a Graph Neural Network (GNN) framework for the classification of finite groups according to their solvability. Using graph representations associated with finite groups, including Cayley graphs (CG), the proposed model is trained to distinguish solvable and non-solvable groups using structural graph information alone. The framework is evaluated on groups outside the training dataset in order to investigate the extent to which GNNs can learn algebraic properties arising in group theory. More broadly, the present work explores the relationship between algebraic structure and graph-based geometric representations of finite groups. The present study is intended as a proof-of-concept investigation of whether GNNs can learn algebraic properties of finite groups from graph-based representations

Keywords: finite groups, solvability, Cayley graphs, graph neural networks, group theory, graph representation learning.

Introduction

Finite groups may be studied abstractly through their algebraic operations [1]. However, an important result in group theory, known as Cayley's theorem [1], states that every finite group is isomorphic to a subgroup of a symmetric group. Consequently, finite groups can be represented concretely as permutation groups, providing a convenient framework for their computational construction and manipulation.

Among the many structural properties of finite groups, solvability [1] occupies a central role in algebra. Informally, a solvable group can be decomposed through a sequence of successively simpler abelian quotient groups. In this sense, solvability may be regarded as a generalization of the notion of commutativity. More formally, let G be a finite group and let $[G, G]$ denote its commutator subgroup. The derived series of G is defined recursively by $G^{(0)} = G$, $G^{(n+1)} =$

$[G^{(n)}, G^{(n)}]$. A finite group is called solvable if its derived series eventually reaches the trivial subgroup. That is, there exists an integer k such that $G^{(k)} = \{e\}$.

Examples of solvable groups include cyclic, dihedral and quaternion groups. In addition, the symmetric groups S_n and alternating groups A_n are solvable for $n \leq 4$. In contrast, for $n \geq 5$, both S_n and A_n are non-solvable. In particular, the alternating group A_5 is the smallest non-solvable simple group.

Although solvability is fundamentally an algebraic property, the present work investigates whether this property is reflected in the structure of the associated Cayley graph (CG) [2].

Let G be a finite group and let $S \subseteq G \setminus \{e\}$ be a generating set. The CG associated with G and S , denoted $\Gamma(G, S)$, is the graph whose vertices correspond to the elements of G , and where two vertices $g, h \in G$ are connected whenever $h = s \cdot g$ for some $s \in S$. CGs provide a geometric and combinatorial representation of finite groups.

The present work investigates whether solvability, despite being defined algebraically through commutator subgroups and derived series, is reflected in structural patterns within the associated CG. This perspective motivates the use of graph neural networks (GNNs) [3], which are designed to learn representations from graph-structured data.

Methodology

The dataset was constructed from several standard families of finite groups, including cyclic, dihedral, quaternion, symmetric and alternating groups. These families provide both solvable and non-solvable examples spanning different algebraic structures and group orders. In particular, symmetric and alternating groups become non-solvable for $n \geq 5$, thereby supplying natural non-solvable instances for the classification task. Each group was generated computationally as a permutation group from a prescribed set of generators.

Due to the computational requirements associated with generating large groups and constructing their corresponding CGs, the dataset size was intentionally limited. The resulting dataset contained 67 solvable groups and 14 non-solvable groups and was partitioned into training, validation and test subsets. Although the overall dataset was dominated by solvable groups, the class imbalance was substantially less pronounced in the training set, which contained 12 solvable groups and 6 non-solvable groups, corresponding to a solvable-to-non-solvable ratio of 2:1. The training set was used to learn the model parameters, the validation set was used to compare alternative GNN architectures and select the best-performing model, and the test set was reserved for the final evaluation of the selected architecture. As the primary objective of the present work is to investigate the feasibility of learning solvability from graph representations, the study should be regarded as a proof-of-concept experiment rather than a large-scale benchmarking study. The group families and order ranges included in each subset are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1

Family	Training	Validation	Test
Cyclic	$C_2 - C_4$	$C_5 - C_{21}$	$C_{22} - C_{35}$
Dihedral	$D_3 - D_5$	$D_6 - D_{21}$	$D_{22} - D_{25}$
Quaternion	$Q_2 - Q_5$	$Q_6 - Q_7$	$Q_8 - Q_9$
Symmetric	$S_4 - S_7$	$S_8 - S_9$	$S_{10} - S_{11}$
Alternating	$A_4 - A_7$	$A_8 - A_9$	$A_{10} - A_{11}$

For each generated group together with its associated generating set, the corresponding CG was constructed according to the definition introduced in the previous section. These CGs served as graph-structured inputs to the GNN.

Each CG was represented as a graph object consisting of node features, edge connectivity information, and a solvability label. For each vertex, the node feature vector comprised the vertex degree together with the order of the underlying group. Edge connectivity information was encoded through the adjacency structure of the CG, as determined by the generating set.

The proposed framework employed a GNN architecture based on graph convolutional layers. The input feature dimension was 2, corresponding to the node feature vector [degree, group order], and the output dimension was 2, corresponding to the solvable and non-solvable classes. The network consisted of two graph convolutional layers followed by global mean pooling and two fully connected layers. ReLU activation was applied after each graph convolutional layer and after the first fully connected layer. Several hidden representation dimensions were considered, ranging from 2 to 64 neurons. The resulting architectures were compared on the validation set, and the best-performing architecture was selected for the final evaluation.

GNN operate by iteratively updating node representations through local neighborhood aggregation. At each layer, the feature vector associated with a vertex is updated using information from neighboring vertices together with its own current representation:

$$h_v^{(k+1)} = \phi\left(h_v^{(k)} + \text{AGG}(\{h_u^{(k)} : u \in \mathcal{N}(v)\})\right) \quad (1)$$

Here, $h_v^{(k+1)}$ denotes the feature representation of vertex v at layer $k + 1$, $\mathcal{N}(v)$ denotes the neighborhood of v , i.e. all neighbors of v , AGG represents a neighborhood aggregation operation, and ϕ denotes a learnable transformation. Through repeated message-passing operations, local structural information is aggregated into higher-level graph representations, which are subsequently pooled and used for graph-level solvability classification.

If solvable and non-solvable groups exhibit systematic differences in the structure of their associated CGs, then these differences may influence the evolution of the node embeddings through the update rule described in (1). Specifically, the embedding at layer $k+1$ depends not only on the current representation of the vertex but also on the aggregated representations of its neighboring vertices. Consequently, the learned embeddings are determined by the connectivity structure of the graph through repeated neighborhood aggregation. As information propagates across successive layers, increasingly global structural characteristics of the CG become encoded in the node embeddings. A graph-level pooling operation then combines these embeddings into a single representation of the entire graph, which is used by the final classification layer to predict whether the underlying group is solvable or non-solvable.

Model performance was evaluated using Balanced Accuracy (BA) [4]. Unlike standard accuracy, which can be dominated by the larger class, balanced accuracy assigns equal weight to the solvable and non-solvable classes. It is defined as the average of the class-wise recall values:

$$BA = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{TP}{TP + FN} + \frac{TN}{TN + FP} \right) \quad (2)$$

Here, TP and TN denote the numbers of correctly classified solvable and non-solvable groups, respectively, while FP and FN denote the numbers of non-solvable and solvable groups that were misclassified.

Results

Several GNN architectures were evaluated and compared using the BA metric defined in (2). Because the numbers of solvable and non-solvable groups were not necessarily equal, BA was selected as the primary evaluation metric, as it assigns equal weight to both classes. The architectures considered included hidden-layer dimensions ranging from 2 to 64 neurons. For each architecture, the model was trained on the corresponding training set and evaluated on a validation set. The resulting BA values are presented in Table 2.

Table 2

Architecture	BA
(2,2,2)	0.500
(2,4,2)	0.500
(2,8,2)	0.971
(2,16,2)	0.957
(2,32,2)	0.957
(2,64,2)	0.957

The comparison presented in Table 2 indicates that the architecture (2,8,2) achieved the highest BA score among the evaluated models. Consequently, this architecture was selected for the final evaluation. The selected model was subsequently tested on an independent test set consisting of groups not used during training or validation. The corresponding results are summarized in Table 3.

Table 3

Architecture	Solvable		Non-solvable		BA
	TP	FN	TN	FP	
(2,8,2)	14	6	4	0	0.85

The results presented in Table 3 demonstrate that the selected architecture retained strong performance on groups that were not used during training or validation. These findings provide evidence that structural information contained in the CG is informative for predicting solvability and suggest that the learned representations generalize beyond the specific groups included in the training dataset.

Discussion and Limitations

The results suggest that GNNs are capable of learning structural patterns associated with the solvability of finite groups from their corresponding CGs. The observed classification performance indicates that graph-based representations may encode information related to algebraic properties that are traditionally defined through subgroup structure and derived series. Moreover, the model achieved strong performance on groups whose orders exceeded those present in the training set, suggesting that the learned representations capture structural information that extends beyond simple memorization of the training examples.

Nevertheless, several limitations of the present study should be acknowledged.

First, the dataset is relatively small compared with datasets commonly used in machine learning applications. This limitation arises from the computational complexity associated with generating large finite groups and constructing their corresponding CGs. In particular, non-solvable groups tend to have substantially larger orders and more complex structures, making their generation and processing computationally demanding.

Second, the dataset is not intended to provide a comprehensive representation of all finite groups. Instead, it consists primarily of several standard families of groups, including cyclic, dihedral, quaternion, symmetric and alternating groups. Consequently, the trained models may learn family-specific structural patterns that do not necessarily generalize to arbitrary finite groups.

Third, the number of available non-solvable examples is significantly smaller than the number of solvable examples. This class imbalance reflects the practical difficulty of generating large collections of non-solvable groups and may influence the learned decision boundaries.

For these reasons, the present work should be viewed as a proof-of-concept study. Its primary objective is not to establish a definitive classification framework for finite-group solvability, but rather to investigate whether GNNs can extract meaningful algebraic information from graph representations of groups.

Future work may consider substantially larger datasets, additional group families, alternative graph constructions, and more sophisticated GNN architectures. Such investigations may provide further insight into the relationship between algebraic properties of finite groups and the geometric structure of their associated graphs.

References

- [1] Dummit, D. S., and Foote, R. M., *Abstract Algebra*, 3rd ed., John Wiley & Sons, 2004.
- [2] Konstantinova, E., "Some Problems on Cayley Graphs," *Linear Algebra and its Applications*, 429 (2008), 2754–2769.
- [3] Z. Wu, S. Pan, F. Chen, G. Long, C. Zhang and P. S. Yu, "A Comprehensive Survey on Graph Neural Networks," *IEEE Transactions on Neural Networks and Learning Systems*, vol. 32, no. 1, pp. 4–24, Jan. 2021, doi: 10.1109/TNNLS.2020.2978386.
- [4] García, V., Mollineda, R. A., & Sánchez, J. S. (2009). *Index of Balanced Accuracy: A Performance Measure for Skewed Class Distributions*. In N. A. Alexandrov, R. A. M. Santos, & J. S. Sánchez (Eds.), *Pattern Recognition and Image Analysis* (Lecture Notes in Computer Science, Vol. 5524, pp. 441–448). Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg.
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